

Electrophilic Aromatic Substitution Reactions. Part-II. Iodination of Aniline, Phenol and Anisole with Iodine Monochloride in Presence and Absence of Sodium Lauryl Sulphate in Aqueous Methanol—A Comparative Kinetic Study

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The kinetics of iodination of aniline, phenol and anisole have been studied by iodine monochloride in 30% (v/v) aqueous methanol in presence and absence of anionic surfactant. The reaction shows first order dependence in $[ICl]$ and $[substrate]$ each and overall second order. The effects of perchloric acid and sodium chloride have been investigated. Dielectric constant effect on the reaction rate constant has been tested with methanol and DMF. Attempts have been made to ascertain the species responsible for iodination. On the basis of the results of the kinetic study, a suitable mechanism has been proposed and discussed. The activation parameters are consistent with the proposed mechanism.

In continuation to our earlier studies¹, the title investigation has been undertaken to compare the reactivities of aniline, phenol and anisole, which are basic, acidic and neutral respectively, towards electrophilic substitution. Survey of literature revealed that no attempt has been made to study this comparison using iodinating agent, iodine monochloride. The aim of conducting the reactions in presence of anionic micelles, like sodium lauryl sulphate (NaLS), is to gain more insight into the nature of iodinating species and to compare the reactivities of aniline, phenol and anisole in presence and absence of micelles. Much information can be derived regarding the active species in the substitution or oxidation reactions because a new reaction medium is generated by these micelles in which reactants are concentrated at the detergent-water interface. To our knowledge this is the first systematic comparative kinetic study of these three different substrates in methanol-water medium.

Experimental

Double-distilled water, methanol (B. D. H.) and DMF (AnalaR) were used in all the reactions. Aniline, phenol, anisole and NaLS (all AnalaR) were used after purification. Standard iodine monochloride was prepared by the procedure given elsewhere¹.

All the three substrates were iodinated in methanol-water and DMF-water mixtures containing an excess of hydrogen ion and chloride ion in order to minimise the effect of small amount of chloride ion

formed during substitution and to prevent the rapid hydrolysis of iodine monochloride on which it furnishes iodic acid with separation of iodine².

where, ArH = aniline, phenol and anisole.

All the experiments were carried out by adopting the condition $[sub]_0 \gg [ICl]_0$ under which reactions followed pseudo-first order rate law. Progress of the reaction was followed by estimating the unreacted iodine monochloride at regular intervals by iodometric method. Rate constants were reproducible to within $\pm 2\%$ and the reactions were followed upto three half-life periods. The results were calculated using a linear least-squares program on a mini computer.

The products of iodination of aniline, phenol and anisole were characterised by preparing their mono-iodo derivatives and comparing with the authentic samples by tlc and other spot tests³.

Results and Discussion

Pseudo-first order rate constants are found to be unaltered, practically, with varying concentration of iodine monochloride in presence of a large excess of the substrate, which indicate the first order dependence of rate on $[ICl]$. The plots of \log pseudo-first order rate constant against $\log [sub]$ of aniline, phenol and anisole are linear, indicating the first order dependence of reaction rate on $[substrate]$. Hence the rate law can be given by the equation,

$$-d[ICl]/dt = k[substrate][ICl]$$

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE VARIATION ON REACTION RATE CONSTANT AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS^a

[Sub]=0.01 mol dm⁻³, [IOI]=0.001 mol dm⁻³, [HClO₄]=0.4 mol dm⁻³, I=1.4 mol dm⁻³, [NaCl]=1.0 mol dm⁻³, MeOH-H₂O=30:70 (v/v), [Surfactant]=0.02 mol dm⁻³

	Temp. °C	k_2 $\times 10^3$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	r^b	E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^\ddagger^c$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔH^\ddagger^c kJ mol ⁻¹	log A
Aniline	20	10.66	0.9995	61.62	61.6	59.10	10.01
	25	16.66	(0.9999)	(57.20)	(75.7)	(54.68)	(9.28)
	30	24.55					
	40	54.02					
Phenol	20	2.86	0.9999	48.97	115.0	46.45	7.19
	30	5.63	(0.9971)	(62.60)	(70.6)	(60.08)	(9.55)
	40	10.38					
	45	13.90					
Anisole	30	$k_2 \times 10^3$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹ 2.52	0.9885	56.97	117.0	53.85	7.12
	40	5.30	(0.9944)	(59.93)	(106.2)	(57.41)	(7.68)
	45	6.82					
	50	10.97					

^aValues in the paranthesis refer to micelle catalysed reactions. ^b r =Reg. coffs. for Arrhenius plots. ^cAt 30°.

Second order overall rate constants are obtained by dividing the pseudo-first order rate constants by substrate concentration. The activation parameters, for the three substrates, are calculated at 30° (Table 1), which affords the comparison between the rates of aniline, phenol and anisole towards iodination under similar conditions.

Dependence of the rate on acid concentration: The effect of hydrogen ion on the rates of reaction has been demonstrated over a wide range of concentrations (0.1–2.5 M). In all the three cases, perchloric acid was used as the source of hydrogen ion. The rates of iodination of aniline and phenol are inversely proportional to hydrogen ion concentration, whereas the rates are found to be independent of hydrogen ion concentration in case of anisole. Independence of rate on acid concentration, in case of anisole, confirms that the species iodinated is anisole itself. At very high concentrations of hydrogen ion, the small decrement in the rate of iodination is, probably, due to hydrogen bonding of the ether-oxygen and the formation of hydrogen-bonded complex which is less susceptible to electrophilic attack. In case of phenol and aniline, plots of $\log k_1$ vs $\log [\text{acid}]$ (Fig. 1) are straight lines with unit negative slope, which confirms the inverse dependence of rate on acid concentration. The inverse dependence of rate on hydrogen ion concentration is interpreted to mean that the species iodinated is not phenol but the phenoxide ion,

Since aniline is basic, first it will be protonated in presence of acid, and deprotonated in a rapid equilibrium step to give free aniline which, actually, participates in the iodination,

So in the case of aniline, the inverse dependence of rate on hydrogen ion concentration indicates that the species undergoing substitution is free aniline.

Fig. 1. Plots of $\log k_1$ vs $\log [\text{HClO}_4]$ for (A) aniline, (B) phenol and (C) anisole.

Dependence of the rate on chloride ion concentration: Rates of substitution, for all the three substrates, showed a decrement with an increase in the chloride ion concentration, and also their rates varied linearly with the expression $K_1/(K_1 + [\text{Cl}^-])$ $[\text{Cl}^-]$, where K_1 is the equilibrium constant for iododichloride ion dissociation,

and the relation

$$[ICl]_{eq} = [ICl]_{st} - [ICl]_2$$

where the subscripts eq and st refer to equilibrium (actual) and the stoichiometric (titratable) concentrations, respectively. The relation holds

$$[ICl]_{eq} = [ICl]_{st} \times K_1 / (K_1 + [Cl^-])$$

when reactions are conducted with different initial chloride ion concentrations, the rates are found to be proportional to $K_1 / (K_1 + [Cl^-]) [Cl^-]$; this is evident from Table 2.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARYING [NaCl] ON REACTION RATE CONSTANT

[Sub]=0.01 mol dm⁻³, [ICl]=0.001 mol dm⁻³, [HClO₄]=0.4 mol dm⁻³, MeOH-H₂O=30:70 (v/v)

Aniline*		Phenol**		Anisole**	
[NaCl] mol dm ⁻³	k ₁ × 10 ³ s ⁻¹	[NaCl] mol dm ⁻³	k ₁ × 10 ³ s ⁻¹	[NaCl] mol dm ⁻³	k ₁ × 10 ³ s ⁻¹
0.6	5.89	0.4	2.86	0.2	28.30
1.0	2.75	0.6	1.80	0.4	10.40
1.2	2.04	0.8	0.79	0.6	5.82
1.4	1.66	1.0	0.56	0.8	3.82

*Temp.=25°, I=1.9 mol dm⁻³. **Temp.=30°, I=1.4 mol dm⁻³.

Inverse dependence of rate on [Cl⁻] gives an evidence for the participation of ICl₂ in the iodination, in the form of H₃OI⁺ from the equation,

Dependence of the rate on [NaLS]: Keeping the generalisation that a cation-dipole reaction would be catalysed by an anionic micelle, the authors attempted the iodination in the presence of NaLS, which forms anionic micelles. Rates of iodination of aniline, phenol and anisole are found to be catalysed by the surfactant. Table 3 shows the effect of added surfactant on the rate of iodination at a given ionic strength, solvent composition and temperature. A sigmoid curve is obtained when *k*_{obs} and [detergent] are correlated. In case

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF VARYING [NaLS] ON REACTION RATE CONSTANT

[Sub]=0.01 mol dm⁻³, [ICl]=0.001 mol dm⁻³, [NaCl]=1.0 mol dm⁻³, [HClO₄]=0.4 mol dm⁻³, Temp.=30°, MeOH-H₂O=30:70 (v/v)

[NaLS] mol dm ⁻³	Aniline × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	Phenol × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	Anisole* × 10 ³ min ⁻¹
0.000	14.7	33.8	36.4
0.005	14.9	41.1	38.1
0.010	15.1	44.2	45.0
0.015	16.8	41.6	50.5
0.020	15.6	33.6	52.9
0.030	16.9	39.6	65.6
0.040	19.0	42.2	60.5
0.050	18.8	48.5	73.7
0.060	—	40.8	—
0.070	18.6	38.5	76.2

*[NaCl]=0.4 mol dm⁻³, 100% aq. medium.

of aniline and phenol, two maxima are noted in the curve at 0.015 and 0.04 M for aniline and 0.01 and 0.05 M for phenol, whereas only a single maximum is noted for anisole at 0.03 M, probably because of its neutral nature. Because of binding between H₃OI⁺ and the negatively charged micelle, the non-covalent binding of substrates to micellar phase is greater. Since the shape of micellar phase changes with the increase in [NaLS] because of its complexation with the substrate, the binding of H₃OI⁺ to micellar phase becomes weaker than non-covalent binding. Thus rate maxima are attributed to binding of H₃OI⁺ and stabilisation of positive charge on the transition state by the anionic micellar phase. From Table 3 it is evident that though there is catalysis, the increase in the rate does not follow a regular trend, and the lowest values of rate constants obtained in some cases with the increase in [NaLS] are greater than that observed in absence of micelles. In aqueous methanol the participation of ICl as H₃OI⁺ has already been supported by the chloride ion effect. The incorporation of surfactant in the halogenation confirmed the iodinating species, H₃OI⁺ and not HOI. The formation of the latter is possible according to the equilibrium,

Dependence of the rate on solvent composition: The effect of varying the composition of organic solvent on the rates of reaction is indicated in Table 4. It is clear that addition of methanol and DMF has a pronounced retarding effect on the rates of these reactions. Azoro⁴ reported a similar finding from their studies of the electrophilic addition of *para*-substituted-styrenes. The net effect of the added organic solvent, in all the three cases, is to reduce the polarity of the reaction medium. Accordingly, these rate reductions are due to a decrease in the ability of solvent to solvate the polar transition state formed in the rate-determining step. The rates of reactions have been measured in various percentages of DMF-water and methanol-water mixtures. The rate constants are found to be greater in methanol-water which implies that solvent plays a more important role in the stabilisation of transition state than in providing an ionic environment. This observation is in accordance with the Ingold rule⁵. It means that solvent participates to different degrees in the bond-breaking and -making processes and that water-methanol are able to do it much more effectively than DMF. Since these reactions are faster in methanol, it is reasonable to conclude that the entropy change for this reaction plays a dominant role. The plots of log *k*₁ vs 1/*D* are found to be linear. The rates of reactions in the three cases are found to increase with increasing dielectric constant (*D*) of the medium. This indicates that the transition state is more polar than the reactant state in these substitution reactions.

Temperature effect and activation parameters: Rates of reactions increased with the increase in

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF SOLVENT COMPOSITION ON REACTION RATE CONSTANT

[Sub]=0.01 mol dm⁻³, [I₂]=0.001 mol dm⁻³, [NaCl]=1.0 mol dm⁻³, [HClO₄]=0.4 mol dm⁻³

Aniline				Phenol				Anisole			
DMF (25°)		MeOH* (25°)		DMF (25°)		MeOH** (30°)		DMF (40°)		MeOH** (30°)	
%(v/v)	$k_1 \times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$	%(v/v)	$k_1 \times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$	%(v/v)	$k_1 \times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$	%(v/v)	$k_1 \times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$	%(v/v)	$k_1 \times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$	%(v/v)	$k_1 \times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$
10	28.37	20	35.20	10	75.00	30	23.61	5	22.16	30	10.40
20	11.76	30	27.48	20	18.33	40	9.60	10	8.86	40	3.65
30	4.48	40	12.78	30	3.00	50	3.40	20	2.75	50	1.09
40	1.87	50	5.79	40	0.82	60	1.07	30	2.18	60	0.27

* [HClO₄]=0.2 mol dm⁻³. ** [NaCl]=0.4 mol dm⁻³.

temperature. Reactions have been studied in methanol-water mixture (30%, v/v) at different temperatures (20–50°) both in presence and absence of micelles. The negative entropy values and the magnitudes of frequency factor indicate the bimolecular nature of these reactions. The relatively small values of ΔH^\ddagger and large negative values ΔS^\ddagger in presence and absence of NaLS, are consistent with reaction which proceeds through highly organised transition state in which bond formations are well advanced. In conclusion, the activation parameters, in particular $-\Delta S^\ddagger$, are consistent with the proposed activated complex.

Based on the experimental data the following mechanism is proposed,

The semistable intermediate [σ -complex] proposed in the mechanism for phenol, aniline and anisole differs in the stability and reactivity. The intermediate in the case of phenol would be a neutral quinol⁶. For aniline the intermediate would be iminoquinolhydrochloride and for anisole the intermediate is oxonium salt without any special electronic or steric stabilising features⁷. The

intermediate in the iodination of phenol could be present at a stationary concentration which is less likely for the intermediates of iodination of aniline and anisole. The order of reactivity towards electrophilic iodination is found to be aniline > phenol > anisole which is in accordance with the proposed mechanism.

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